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SUPEROVULATION, OPU-IVP, AND EMBRYO TRANSFER

Long-term haematological analysis in pigs derived from assisted reproductive technologies

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Rising livestock demand has increased use of assisted reproductive technologies (ART). Evidence indicates long-term effects of ART on molecular physiology and metabolism. This study explores ART's impact on haematological parameters in a colony of pigs from 1 to 5 years of age. Animals were born after artificial insemination (AI) and transfer of embryos *in vitro* produced with (RF-IVP) or without (C-IVP) oviductal and uterine fluids during *in vitro* fertilization and embryo culture media (París-Oller et al., J Anim Sci and Biotechnol, 2021). Pigs were maintained under identical conditions and sampled every six months. Number of animals in each group decreased throughout life: 33 to 9 (AI); 22 to 10 (C-IVP); and 14 to 4 (RF-IVP). The number of blood samples was the same as the number of animals and were collected via jugular venipuncture in lithium heparin tubes and immediately transported to laboratory. A haematology analyzer (Siemens ADVIA® 120, USA) assessed red blood cell (RBC) count, haemoglobin concentration (HB), haematocrit (HCT), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC), cell haemoglobin concentration mean (CHCM), red blood cell distribution width (RDW), haemoglobin concentration distribution width (HDW), white blood cell (WBC) count; and the differential count of neutrophils, lymphocytes, monocytes, eosinophils, and basophils. Reticulocyte percentage, mean corpuscular volume of reticulocytes (MCVr), haemoglobin content in reticulocytes (CHR) and platelet count were analyzed. Data were analyzed by mixed-effects model and likelihood-ratio test to determine effects of age, group and sex on the variables. Post-hoc test for multiple comparisons Tukey's method were used. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. Age affected all variables. MCH, CH, CHCM, WBC, and platelet indices (MPV, MPC, MPM, PMDW) increased through life. Biphasic trajectories occurred in MCV, HCT, RBC, neutrophil counts, monocyte counts, PLT counts, and lymphocytes (second-year decline followed by increase). Progressive decline with age was observed in monocyte percentage and reticulocyte parameters. Irregular oscillatory patterns dominated HB, RDW, MCHC, CHDW, HDW, eosinophil and basophil parameters, and advanced platelet indices (large PLT, PCT, PDW, MCVr, PCDW). HCT, RBC, and HB reached lowest values in AI group, highest in RF-IVP. HCM, MCHC, and lymphocyte percentage showed lowest means in AI, highest in C-IVP. RDW, WBC, neutrophil parameters, and lymphocyte count were lowest in C-IVP, highest in AI. Monocyte count exhibited lowest values in C-IVP, highest in RF-IVP group. CH and PCDW were higher in females than males, whereas HDW, PDW, MPC were higher in males. Long-term results confirm slight persisting haematological differences in naturally and artificially conceived pigs, although the clinical relevance is unnoticeable.

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